

The impact of women in top-level management positions on an organization's leadership strategies

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Abstract

An organization's decision-making capacity is entirely contingent on its management. Competent and productive executives can have a significant impact on the performance of a business. Women's diverse thinking skills in management contribute to achieving success. Seeks to demonstrate the significant impact of women in the organization's decision-making and leadership. The organization performs successfully due to the influence of female leaders and their cognitive abilities. The portrayal of women executives in a company contributes to its financial and social stability. The governing body gathers detailed information about the women in leadership positions within the organization. This information was gathered through a survey conducted with 80 individuals. Gather primary data about women leaders in the Jordanian organization and do statistical analysis using the SPSS software. This analysis is founded on the correlation between the independent variable and the dependent variable within this subject. The majority of males who participated in the survey acknowledged the significant influence of women executives in management. The woman's leadership management perspective enhances the execution of leadership methods within the organization. The article explores the decision-making skills of women executives and their significance in enhancing organizational performance in a competitive market.

Keywords: women empowerment, Top level management, managing strategy, leadership, encouragement, working culture.

1. INTRODUCTION

A functioning business's performance is contingent upon the tactics executed by the management. Most decisions are taken by senior management and then communicated to lower levels of the company. This method involves the management guiding the organization to operate efficiently (Birindelli, Iannuzzi, & Savioli, 2019). Major decisions in an organization are primarily based on the perspectives or strategies of the individuals involved. This involves evaluating the cognitive capacities of men through decision-making, comparison, and analysis, but excluding other genders such as females. Women's skills and abilities can significantly impact leadership and create additional chances for the organization.

Figure 1: Percentage of Women in Leadership Has Changed Over the Past 15 Years

(Source: LinkedIn, 2023)

The figure above illustrates that women's success and active participation in the organization can lead to significant beneficial improvements. Women's leadership in healthcare sectors has a significant impact on 62% of top performance in that industry (LinkedIn, 2023). This impacts women's industrial performance in marketing, social, and financial aspects by enabling them to make effective adaptive decisions based on critical analysis. It is influenced by the 27% effective leadership performance of women in the organization.

Accordingly, the study aims to show the influential role of women in the decision-making and leading actions of the organization.

2. Research Objectives

RO 1: To depict the leadership abilities of women in managing the organization.

RO 2: To assess the influence of women's leadership styles on enhancing organizational performance.

RO 3: To identify the factors that prevent women from actively participating in organizational management.

RO 4: To discuss the benefits of including women in organizational management.

3. Research Questions

RQ 1: What advantages result from women taking the lead in managerial decision-making?

RQ 2: How can women effectively use cutting-edge technologies in organizational management?

RQ 3: What is the significance of developing an efficient leadership strategy in enhancing organizational performance?

RQ 4: How does women's decision-making impact the overall structure of an organization?

4. Literature review

4.1 Leadership Management by Women

Figure 2: Leadership management by Women
(Source: Influenced by Birindelli, Iannuzzi, & Savioli, 2019)

The working performance of an organization directly depends on the leading strategies and decisions taken by the management. Based on the views of Birindelli, Iannuzzi, and Savioli (2019), the decisions of women leaders can provide effective encouragement to the employees. The reliability and comfort need of the employees are reflected in their performance in the organization. The effective decisions of the management influence the marketing performance of the organization. In a recent study in 2021, about 5 percent of the women made the climb to a higher position in their management (Irijmets, 2023). On the other hand, Maida & Weber (2022) argued that the diversity in leadership by female leaders impacts the financial performance of the firm. The thinking ability of women makes a comparison of all relateable circumstances in the organization and takes an effective decision for the welfare of the organization, as shown in Figure 2, with the different leadership styles adopted by women.

4.2 Influence of Women Leaders in An Organization

Figure 3: Influence of women leaders in an organization
(Source: Influenced by Chen et al.2019)

The capability of an organization is analyzed through the efficiency of performing the production and service-providing activities, as shown in figure 3. As commented by Richard et al. (2019), the top-level management of an organization constructs the strength and the opportunity of the organization. In this way, the efficiency of the employees or laborers working in the organization impacts its performance. Women leaders in the top-level management of an organization understand the mindset of the employees and implement the best strategy. In a recent study of 2021, about 26 percent of the CEOs and managing directors of organizations are women, which increased from 15 percent in 2019 (Irmets, 2023). However, Chen et al. (2019) stated that the interactive involvement of women in management implements rapid innovative technologies. These technologies help the organization face all the social and economic issues.

4.3 Obstacles Encountered by Women in Management

The effective and adaptive technologies implemented by the leaders in the organization grow the performance of the organization. In these women, leaders have a huge impact on making effective decisions for the performance of the organization. Based on the views of Dhar, Harymawan, & Sarkar (2022), the detailed investigation and the direct involvement of the leaders make the leading strategies more effective. In modern society, women are not fully considered to be involved in decision-making authority. Over that, they are considered to be managing their husband, children, and other family members. This leads them to provide diversified and creative ideas to the management of the organization through active involvement. On the other hand, Dashper (2020) argued that gender equality in the management of an organization helps in creating creative ideas. The ability of the women in the family is to understand the mindset of the members. This ability in the leadership management of an organization helps them to make effective decisions by assuming all the mindsets of the employers.

4.4 Behavioral Theory

Figure 4: Behavioral theory of leadership

(Source: Influenced by Dashper, 2020)

Behavioral theory focuses on the concepts of all involved in a work. The behavior of the involved parties is easily understandable from their interactions with them. The leaders in the management of an organization make the development through interacting with the working environment and working factors. The women understand all the necessities of the employees and the organization and make effective decisions for the organization's welfare.

5. Methodology

The methodologies used for making the relationship between the women leaders in the organization collect effective information from the primary source of data. These sources mainly consist of the opinions of the top-level management of an organization and the employees of the organization. These opinions are collected through the valuable responses of 80 respondents, who answered 13 questions reflecting on the implementation benefits of women leaders and women's decisions in the management of an organization. These questions in the data-gathering process of the study are represented in descriptive terms. These valuable opinions of the respondents are analyzed using a deductive approach. This data refers to an analysis of the gathered information through inductive philosophy (Kumar, 2018). The final collection of the data is statistically examined and analyzed through the SPSS analytical tool, representing quantitative

analysis of the data. This statistical analysis is a quantitative analysis of the data and relates to the hypothetical investigation.

6. Finding and analysis

6.1 Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis 1

H1: The examination of the internal and the external circumstances of the organization are fully operated by the management of the organization.

H0: The examination of the internal and the external circumstances of the organization are not operated by the management of the organization.

Hypothesis 2

H1: The management team of the organization directly impacts the leading strategies implemented on the employees.

H0: The management team of the organization does not impact the leading strategies implemented on the employees.

Hypothesis 3

H1: Critical thinking abilities of women help the organization to perform well in the competitive market.

H0: A critical thinking ability of women does not help the organization to perform well in the competitive market.

6.2 Demographic data

The demographic data collected for this study includes information on the age, gender, and income of the participants.

6.2.1 Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Between 20 to 35	8	10.0	10.0	10.0
	Between 36 to 45	56	70.0	70.0	80.0
	Between 46 to 55	16	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	80	100.0	100.0	

Table 1: Age analysis

(Source: SPSS)

As pointed out in Table 1, it shows the statistical analysis of the age division of the respondents to the survey. Among the 80 respondents, the majority of them—56 of them—were from the age range of 36 to 45, amounting to 70 percent of the total responses taken. This response gives the best feedback from people about women's leadership in the management of an organization.

6.2.2 Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	16	20.0	20.0	20.0
	Male	40	50.0	50.0	70.0
	Prefer not to say	24	30.0	30.0	100.0
	Total	80	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Gender analysis

(Source: SPSS)

As pointed out in the above table 2, it shows the statistical analysis of the gender division of the respondents to the survey. Among the 80 respondents, the majority were male, with 40 of them being of the male gender, amounting to 50 percent of the total responses taken. This response gives the best feedback from people about women's leadership in the management of an organization.

6.2.3 Monthly income

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	above USD 600	8	10.0	10.0	10.0
	Between USD 200 to 350	48	60.0	60.0	70.0
	Between USD 350 to 600	24	30.0	30.0	100.0
	Total	80	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Analysis of monthly income

(Source: SPSS)

As pointed out in the above table 3, it shows the statistical analysis of the earning division of the respondents to the survey. Out of the 80 respondents, 48 of them belonged to the income bracket of USD 200 to 350, which represented 60% of the total responses. This response gives the best feedback from people about women's leadership in the management of an organization.

6.3 Descriptive analysis

Descriptive analysis is an essential part of research that entails a methodical review and explanation of data to offer a thorough overview of important characteristics. Researchers in this analytical methodology strive to arrange, condense, and display the primary attributes of a dataset. Descriptive analysis usually utilizes statistical variables like mean, median, mode, and standard deviation to explain the central tendency and dispersion of the data. This strategy aids researchers in achieving a more profound comprehension of the data and enables them to effectively communicate their findings to a broader audience. Descriptive analysis is the initial phase that offers a straightforward and simple overview of the dataset being studied before more advanced statistical analyses are conducted.

6.3.1 Analysis Hypothesis 1

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.531 ^a	.282	.273	1.52516	.282	30.679	1	78	.000	1.665

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV1
b. Dependent Variable: DV

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	71.364	1	71.364	30.679	.000 ^b
	Residual	181.436	78	2.326		
	Total	252.800	79			

a. Dependent Variable: DV
b. Predictors: (Constant), IV1

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.031	.597		5.077	.000
	IV1	.293	.053	.531	5.539	.000

Table 4: Hypothesis 1

(Source: SPSS)

In the above-represented table 4, it shows the descriptive analysis of hypothesis 1. It includes an assessment of the significance of IV1 with the DV. In the projected descriptive analysis, it shows an R-value of .531 and an r-square of .282. This includes the value of Durbin Watson at 1.665 and a significant value of .000 that is less than the value of .005, so it is significant to establish a strong relationship between leadership and the management authority of an organization.

6.3.2 Analysis Hypothesis 2

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.317 ^a	.101	.089	1.70717	.101	8.740	1	78	.004	1.417

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV2
b. Dependent Variable: DV

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	25.473	1	25.473	8.740	.004 ^b
	Residual	227.327	78	2.914		
	Total	252.800	79			

a. Dependent Variable: DV
b. Predictors: (Constant), IV2

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.064	.747		5.438	.000
	IV2	.202	.068	.317	2.956	.004

Table 5: Hypothesis 2

(Source: SPSS)

In the above represented table 5, it shows the descriptive analysis of hypothesis 2. It includes an assessment of the significance of IV2 with the DV. In the projected descriptive analysis, it shows an R-value of .317 and an r-square of .101. This includes the value of Durbin Watson at 1.417 and a significant value of .000 that is less than the value of .005, so it is significant to establish a strong relationship between the managing authorities and the performance of an organization.

6.3.3 Analysis Hypothesis 3

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.256 ^a	.066	.054	1.74014	.066	5.485	1	78	.022	1.141

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV3
b. Dependent Variable: DV

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16.608	1	16.608	5.485	.022 ^b
	Residual	236.192	78	3.028		
	Total	252.800	79			

a. Dependent Variable: DV
b. Predictors: (Constant), IV3

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.743	.652		7.275	.000
	IV3	.200	.085	.256	2.342	.022

Table 6: Hypothesis 3

(Source: SPSS)

In the above represented table 6, it shows the descriptive analysis of hypothesis 3. It includes an assessment of the significance of IV1 for the DV. In the projected descriptive analysis, it shows an R-value of.531 and an r-square of.282. This includes the value of Durbin Watson at 1.665 and a significant value of.000 that is less than the value of.005, so it is significant to establish a strong relationship between leadership in the management authority of an organization.

7. DISCUSSION

The statistical analysis makes the collection of the information from the primary source of collection of information from the top-level management of an organization and the employees of the organization. As commented by Erskine, & Bilimoria, (2019), the managing and handling of employees through the women perspective makes transformative changes in the organization. It also happens equally in case for decision making and leading the working factors of the organization of India. The analysis and the solution of the problems through the diversified and collective mindset of the women of the society make the working factor perform qualifiedly. The response of the individuals from every age group and gender division provides the hypothetical valuation of the analysis on the performance of women in the managing authorities of the organization. This statistical analysis represents the better performing of software-based programmers for solving management and leadership issues in the organization by the implemented strategies of the women leaders.

8. CONCLUSION

The performance of the women leaders in the top-level management provides necessary and large impact on the organization's performance. This includes the decision-making, comparing, and analyzing the psychological thinking abilities of men excluding the other genders like females. The skills and abilities of women can often make influential leadership and provide more opportunities to the organization. The critical analyzing and patience level of the women in interacting with the employees to get best knowledge about their behaviors in the working environment. This ability makes the organization get efficient productivity skill from the employees to perform well in the market. Genders equality in the management of an organization helps in making creative ideas. The ability of the women in the family is to understand the mindset of the members. This ability in the leadership management of an organization helps them to make effective decisions by assuming all the mindsets of the employee.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

According on the discussion and conclusion in the paper, here are some recommendations:

Advocate for and strengthen policies that support diversity in organizational leadership. Promote the selection and assistance of women in high-level managerial roles to leverage the significant effects revealed in the statistical evaluation.

Implement customized leadership development programs designed specifically for women to improve their skills and talents. These programs should emphasize decision-making, critical thinking, and interpersonal skills to prepare women leaders for the demands of top-level management.

Establish an inclusive work atmosphere that celebrates diversity and provides equal chances for all employees, regardless of gender. This entails confronting biases and stereotypes present in the organizational culture.

Establish mentorship programs and support structures for female leaders. This will aid in information transfer, skill enhancement, and offer a venue for sharing experiences, so fostering the professional development of women in leadership positions.

Continuous study and assessment should be promoted to assess the performance of women in leadership roles. This may include regular evaluations of organizational dynamics, employee contentment, and overall effectiveness to measure the lasting influence of gender-inclusive leadership.

Support educational programs that highlight the significance of gender equality in leadership. This may involve implementing training programs, workshops, and awareness campaigns to address and counteract stereotypes and biases within the organization.

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